

Effect of Green Manufacturing on Performance of Manufacturing Firms in Kenya

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Abstract

The primary purpose of this article was to determine the effect of green manufacturing on the performance of manufacturing firms in Kenya. This study was anchored on resource dependence theory. The study was based on a positivist approach while employing an explanatory research design. The study targeted 757 manufacturing firms in Kenya registered. Stratified and simple random sampling was used to select a sample size of 386 firms. Primary data was collected using a questionnaire that was addressed to firms' operational and procurement managers. Inferential statistics using regression and correlation analysis were applied to assist in examining the relationship between the research variable. The findings showed that green manufacturing had a significant and positive effect on the performance of manufacturing firms in Kenya. Therefore, it is of utmost necessary for the firms to use inputs with relatively low environmental impacts.

Keywords: Green Manufacturing, Performance, Firms, Green Supply,

1. Introduction

Globally, consumers and governmental entities have begun to demand that processes, products, and services be environmentally friendly, it is essential that managers identify and implement environmental sustainability practices that extend throughout their supply chains. The world manufacturing managers are responsible for the performance of the organizations for which they work (Green *et al.*, 2012).both manufacturing and service organizations consider the impact production processes have on the environment and the economic viability of the firm as well as on the environmental performance. They link the success of a manufacturing firm to the supply chain and there are concerted efforts by businesses to adopt green production strategies. Customers and governmental entities have begun to demand that processes, products, and services be environmentally friendly, therefore making it essential for managers to identify and implement environmental sustainability practices that extend throughout the supply chain (Mud gal, Shankar, Talib & Raj, 2010). A lot of efforts are being put into minimizing environmental footprints of the manufacturing industry to enhance environmental protection and sustainable development. It is on this basis that, green manufacturing is now gaining popularity as a management approach in facilitating matters related to environmental issues and firms 'performance.

Green manufacturing (gm), is a process that integrates product and product design with issues of manufacturing, planning and control in such a manner to identify, quantify, access and manage the flow of environmental waste with the goal of reducing and ultimately minimizing environmental impact while also trying to maximize resources efficiency (Melyk *et al.*, 2009). Green manufacturing is defined as a production process that uses inputs with relatively low environmental impacts, which are highly efficient and which generate little or no waste or no pollution. The impacts of processes used in manufacturing products and developing services also vary.

Manufacturing processes may differ in the efficiency of input use, the amount and kind of waste generated, and environmental effects on ecosystems and human health. Such impacts may be reduced by manufacturers through various means, ranging from improvements focusing on individual factors such as amounts and sources of energy used, to integrated approaches such as lean manufacturing techniques, which aim to reduce waste and improve efficiency throughout the manufacturing process.

Green manufacturing converts inputs into output by reducing hazardous substances, increasing energy efficiency in lighting and heating, minimizing waste, actively designing and redesigning green processes (Newman, & Jensen, 2013). Green products generally require fewer resources to manufacture and operate so

that savings can be made on energy, water, fuel and other natural resources. However, Manufacturing firms that have not yet adopted green manufacturing are being phased out of the market due to an increasing aspect of competitive advantage. There is a need for more research in the area as most of the previous studies have not focused on green manufacturing and their link to business performance. A significant number of green manufacturing studies have investigated whether the implementation of green supply chain management strategies leads to enhanced firm performance (Sarkis 2012). Given the inconclusive results of previous studies, it remains unclear if firms that comprehensively adopt green manufacturers perform better.

Hypothesis Development (Review of Literature)

Green manufacturing requires manufacturers to design products that facilitate the reuse, recycle and recovery parts and material components; avoid or reduce the use of hazardous products within the production process; minimize consumption of materials as well as energy (Newman, *et.al* 2013). It is a sustainable form of manufacturing that integrates the life cycle concept, including green designs, production and distribution of raw materials, maintenance and disposal processes which minimize resource depletion. Products are generally produced in a manner that consumes fewer natural resources or uses them more sustainably. They may involve less energy in their manufacture and may consume less energy when being used (Newman, *et.al* 2013).

Preliminary findings on a study that was conducted by Ghazilla, Sakundarini, Abdul-Rashid, Ayub, Olugu, and Musa, (2015) on drivers and barriers analysis for green manufacturing practices in Malaysian Smes used the Delphi survey method to explore, identify and verify the drivers and barriers of green manufacturing practices by obtaining consensus from a panel of experts were required to answer questionnaires in three rounds. The results of this study revealed several barriers and drivers towards the adoption of green manufacturing practices that included among others holistic intervention programmers; high commitment from various stakeholders, support from external stakeholders; internal organization, regulations, good environmental education, competitiveness; culture; use and availability of information.

Another study by Diabat and Govindan (2011), provided an in-depth analysis of the drivers affecting the implementation of green supply chain management. The paper investigated the responsibility of identifying twelve familiar drivers of green manufacturing from the combined assistance of existing literature, industrial managers, and expert opinion in the relevant field. A questionnaire on these familiar drivers was circulated among 120 leading firms in south India, and aided by their replies; a pair-wise comparison was made among the drivers. The analysis resorted to the use of a fuzzy multi-criteria decision making (Mcdm) approach. The obtained results were validated by a two-stage sensitivity analysis of different de-russification methods that are further evaluated through the spearman coefficient and assigning varying weight to the essential top priority drivers of green manufacturing among all standard drivers. The paper concluded with some insight into the future path of green manufacturing in developing countries and an acknowledgment of the study's own limitations.

A separate pilot study conducted by Gezen and Cankaya, (2013) on the effects of green manufacturing and eco-innovation on sustainability performance. Data for the study were collected through a questionnaire-based survey across 53 companies from the automotive, chemistry and electronic sectors in turkey. The empirical model was -tested using regression analysis, to verify the hypothetical relationships of the study. The results of this study indicated that green manufacturing applications have a significant positive impact on environmental performance and social performance. Additionally, eco-process innovation has a significant positive impact on corporate sustainability. However, eco-product innovation was not found to have a significant effect on any of the three types of performance. This indicates a possible link between green manufacturing and performance, however, literature shows that there is limited implementation of green manufacturing practices in developing countries as compared to developed countries. Thus, this study hypothesized that:

H₁ *Green manufacturing significantly affect the performance of manufacturing firms in Kenya*

Theoretical Review**This study was anchored on Resource Dependence Theory**

The resource dependence theory suggests that firms rely on others to provide critical resources, components or capabilities provided by others (Awaysheh & Klassen 2010). The dependence of one party provides the basis for the power of the other (Emerson 1962). Thus, firms with durable bargaining power can exercise control over weaker parties (Crook & Combs 2007). The diffusion of environmental practices in the supply chain can be explained with reference to the power development aspect of the resource dependence theory (Sarkis *et al.* 2011). Depending on their ability to control resources and potential substitutes, firms have several options for securing access to environmental resources. The procuring entity 's ability to motivate suppliers to commit to environmental partnerships is usually based on the supplier 's dependence on the buyer (Min & Galle 2001). Incentives in buyer-supplier relationships can be grouped into competitive incentives, i.e. Suppliers are awarded present and future business based on their performance relative to other suppliers – typically in an arm 's length relationship; and cooperative incentives, i.e. A sharing of the benefits of increased performance within a dyadic buyer-supplier relationship based on their joint performance (Foerstl *et al.* 2015). Hence, environmental monitoring can be considered to consist mainly of competitive incentives while environmental collaboration involves mainly cooperative incentives. A supply chain is a network of all parties involved in the transmission of materials from their original source through manufacturing to the ultimate consumer. The theory is relevant to the study as it informs the green manufacturing variable in this study.

Methodology

This study adopted an explanatory research design using a quantitative approach. The target population for this study was the entire population of 757 manufacturing firms which are registered members of Kenya association of manufacturers (KAM, 2017), and represent 80% are within Nairobi county. Researchers have developed a rule of thumb in determining sample size. For example, Olusola *et al* (2013) argues that a minimum number of 15 in experimental research, 30 in correlational research and a minimum of 100 in survey research is adequate. However, Nachiamis & Nachamis (2012) argued that if the target population is finite, the following formula may be used to determine the sample size. Thus using Nachiamis & Nachamis ,2012) the study calculated a sample of 386. The researcher used a geographical cluster sampling technique to select representatives from each stratum. The primary data collection instrument in this study was a questionnaire. The study collected primary data using structured questionnaires and capture information through a 5-point Likert scale type. Likert scale is an interval scale that specifically uses five anchors of strongly disagrees, disagree, neutral, agree and strongly agree. pilot tests were used to test the validity and reliability testing of the data collection instrument. In this study, reliability was measured using Cronbach alpha. The measurement scale for reliability was tested using Cronbach alpha coefficient for every independent variable and for an alpha (α) of 0.7 and above the instrument was interpreted as reliable (Cronbach, 1951).The study adopted a confirmatory factor analysis to test for construct validity. The regression model below was used to test hypotheses.

$$y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + e$$

y = firm performance

X = Green Manufacturing.

Results

This section presents data analysis, presentation and interpretation of the findings. The section also

highlights the fundamental results of the examination based on which further investigations was attempted to test the hypotheses.

Sample characteristics

The study deemed it essential to highlight procurement manager characteristics since their attributes have a bearing on the performance of manufacturing firms in Kenya. Their characteristic focused on their age, level of education and work experience. The findings are as presented in table 1 As the study reveals, the most of the respondents (45.5%) were of the 41- 50 years age bracket, 22.3% of the respondents specified they belonged to the age category of over 50 years, 17.4% were aged between 21-30 years whereas 14.7% of the respondents indicated that they were 31-40 years. The finding indicates that there was a fair age distribution of the respondents. On respondents' level of education achieved, the research showed that the majority of the respondents as indicated by 91.1% had a university degree whereas 8.9% of the respondents had attained tertiary education. The results suggest that those at the management level in the procurement department have at least a degree or tertiary level of education. Regarding the work experience, 88.4% of the procurement managers have been with the firm for over 3 years, 8% of them for 3 years and 3.6% for 2 years. Overall, the procurement managers have worked with the manufacturing firms for over 3 years.

Table 1 Procurement Manager Characteristics

		Frequency	Percent
Respondents Age	21 - 30 Years	39	17.4
	31- 40 Years	33	14.7
	41 - 50 Years	102	45.5
	Over 50 Years	50	22.3
	Total	224	100
Level of Formal Education	Tertiary	20	8.9
	University	204	91.1
	Total	224	100
Work Experience	2 Years	8	3.6
	3 Years	18	8
	Over 3 Years	198	88.4
	Total	224	100

Descriptive statistics

Firm performance is on the premise that an organization is in possession of productive assets such as human, physical, and capital assets required to accomplish a common purpose (Hayes, 2013). Table 1 highlights the results, There is a possibility that the firms have not aligned their corporate strategies with green supply chain management hence the firms have not elicited an increase in the profit levels. The implication is that the introduction of green supply chain management has not been instrumental in increasing the market share. It could be that the firms have not implemented green supply chain management hence they have not been able to benefit from it entirely. The results suggest that there have not been returns on investment after the introduction of green supply chain management. This could be due to the inability to implement GSCM fully. The implication is that the manufacturing firms have not fully adopted GSCM hence they are unable to elicit changes in the firms' usage of energy resources. In a nutshell, firm performance realized a mean of 1.71, a standard deviation of 0.21. The results suggest that not much change has been elicited in the performance of the manufacturing firms after the introduction of green supply chain management.

Table 1 Firm performance

n=224	Mean	Std. Dev	loadings
Profitability has changed after the introduction of green supply chain management	1.24	0.43	0.71
percentage change in profits after the introduction of green supply chain management	2.24	0.44	0.66
percentage change in market share after the introduction of green supply chain management	1.40	0.49	0.63
percentage change in average return on an investment after the introduction of green supply chain management	2.13	0.66	0.87
percentage change in average sales volume after the introduction of green supply chain management	1.41	0.50	0.90
The direction of change of earnings per share after the introduction of green supply chain management	2.21	0.61	0.66
percentage change in earnings per share after the introduction of green supply chain management	1.17	0.37	0.70
The direction of change of market share after the introduction of green supply chain management	2.29	0.61	0.92
The direction of change of average sales volume after the introduction of green supply chain management	1.24	0.64	0.83
The direction of change of average return on an investment after the introduction of green supply chain management	2.13	0.67	0.77
Direction of change of company's usage of energy resources after introduction of green supply chain management	1.24	0.43	0.73
Firm performance	1.71	0.21	

KMO=.63, Bartlett's Test of Sphericity ($\chi^2=2345.481$, $p=.000$, $CV=57.45\%$, Cronbach's Alpha=0.829)

Green manufacturing describes manufacturing practices that do not harm the environment during any part of the manufacturing process. It advocates efficient, clean, low-carbon, recycling, and takes the road of ecological civilization. As such, the study deemed it essential to establish if the manufacturing firms in Kenya had an emphasis on green manufacturing in their operations. The results of green manufacturing are illustrated in table 2. The results imply that manufacturing firms are not using inputs with relatively low environmental impacts. Besides, there is no focus on product design that facilitates recycling and the firms have not adopted a green procurement policy. This could be detrimental to the overall performance of the manufacturing firms. Evidently, there is low adoption of green technology in manufacturing processes and limited use of inputs that generate little pollution. Further, minimal efforts have been directed towards ensuring that there is minimized consumption of materials as well as energy to minimize resource depletion (mean = 2.39, SD = 0.67). Overall, green manufacturing summed up to a mean of 2.36, the standard deviation of 0.47, skewness of 1.69 and kurtosis of 3.54. Evidently, the manufacturing firms have not emphasized green manufacturing in their processes right from product design, production and the management of waste.

Table 2 Green manufacturing

n=224	Mean	Std. Dev	loadings
The company uses inputs with relatively low environmental impacts	2.21	0.62	0.58
The company uses inputs that generate little pollution	2.25	0.64	0.85
The company uses machines with little air emission	2.18	0.60	0.93
The company has reduced the generation of effluent waste	2.21	0.47	0.63
The company has minimized consumption of materials as well as energy to minimize resource depletion	2.95	2.94	0.69
The company uses product design that facilitates recycling of the parts or material component	2.21	0.56	0.61
The company has adopted a green procurement policy that ...	2.36	0.55	0.84
The company has adopted green technology in manufacturing processes	2.51	1.02	0.85
The company's solid waste is recycled	2.29	0.45	0.60

KMO=.59, Bartlett's Test of Sphericity ($\chi^2=1365.463$, $P=.000$, $CV=60.74\%$, Cronbach's Alpha=0.844)

Inferential Statistics (Hypothesis Testing)

Correlation analysis is carried out in research to ascertain the level to which two factors converge or diverge together depending on the case so as to establish the significance of the relationship. The findings also showed that green manufacturing did have a positive and significant relationship with firm performance ($r = 0.661$, $p\text{-value} = 0.000$). Further, the hypothesis was tested using a linear regression model.

The second (H1) hypothesis postulated that green manufacturing does significantly affect the performance of manufacturing firms in Kenya. The findings in Table 3 showed that green manufacturing has a positive and significant effect on firm performance ($\beta_2 = 0.840$, $p < 0.05$). Hence, the hypothesis was rejected. This can be explained further by assessing the value of the t-test which indicates that green manufacturing would be attributed to the regression model 13 times more compared to the effect of the standard error associated with the estimated coefficient ($t = 13.141$). The findings in Table 4.24 further indicated that the variation in firm performance was attributed by 43.8% change in green manufacturing. Consistent with the findings, Ninlawan *et al.*, (2010) echoed that green manufacturing has the potential of lowering raw material costs, reducing environmental and occupational safety expenses and improving corporate image. Similarly, Defra, (2008) argued that several firms view the application of green manufacturing technologies as instrumental in improving the overall firm performance. In a similar vein, Newman, & Jensen, (2013) stipulated that green manufacturing converts inputs into outputs by reducing hazardous substances, minimizing waste, actively designing and redesigning green processes. Furthermore, Gezen and Cankaya, (2013) concluded that green manufacturing applications have a significant positive impact on environmental performance and social performance.

Table 3 Influence of Green Manufacturing on Performance of Manufacturing Firms in Kenya

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients			correlation
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.	r
(Constant)	0.304	0.157		1.943	0.053	
Green manufacturing	0.840	0.064	0.661	13.141	0.000	.661**
Model Summary statistics						
R	0.661					
R Square	0.438					
Adjusted R Square	0.435					
Std. The error of the Estimate	0.659					
Model fitness statistics (ANOVA results)						
F	172.673					
Sig.	0.000					

a Dependent Variable: firm performance

Conclusion

Green manufacturing exhibited a positive and significant effect on the performance of manufacturing firms. This is despite the low adoption of green manufacturing among targeted manufacturing firms. The results suggest that if the firms would emphasize more on ensuring that their product design facilitates recycling of the material component, concerted efforts towards fully implementing a green procurement policy and discouraging the use of inputs that would cause pollution there would be an improvement in the performance of the manufacturing firms to a great extent. Nevertheless, the firms are yet to fully adopt green manufacturing and capitalize on its benefits to the environment and the firm.

Recommendations

Green manufacturing contributes to improved performance of manufacturing firms. Therefore, it is of utmost necessary for the firms to use inputs with relatively low environmental impacts. Besides, emphasis

needs to be on designing products that are recyclable and generate little pollution. Further, there is also a need for manufacturing firms to ensure there is a reduction in the generation of effluent waste. In addition, there should be concerted efforts towards ensuring that a green procurement policy is fully adopted within the firms.

The study highlighted the critical role played by collaborative capability in moderating the relationship between green supply chain management and the performance of manufacturing firms in Kenya. One direction of future research would be a replication study in other sectors not covered in the study. Furthermore, in terms of methodology, future scholars can conduct a longitudinal study as well as appreciate both the quantitative and qualitative aspects of research. Nonetheless, the thesis has contributed knowledge that is needed for this kind of research.

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